

MEDICAL SCIENCES

PROBLEMS OF LABOR POTENTIAL FORMATION IN UKRAINE IN WAR AND POST-WAR TIMES

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Abstract

Over the past decades, problems with the formation of labor potential have been observed in the country due to low birth rate, high mortality, relatively low average life expectancy, negative population growth, reduced socio-economic standards (low level of average wages, insufficient level of housing provision, etc.). There are deficiencies in creating decent working conditions, providing medical care to workers, and labor migration. All these indicators significantly worsened during the war. During the war, the labor potential of Ukraine was reduced by a third. Almost 8 million people became forced migrants, about 3 million remained in temporarily occupied territories, about 1 million were mobilized into the army and other military formations. During the war, the demand for labor decreased sharply due to the inability to work in war zones, forced migration, relocation or closure of enterprises, reduced demand for goods and services, problems with logistics and uncertainty about the future. Increasing the level of employment should become a central issue of post-war reconstruction, reintegration and processes of returning to peace.

Keywords: labor potential, labor and forced migration, wartime.

Definition of the problem, analysis of the latest research and publications. Labor potential - the current and projected future labor opportunities of a country, region or enterprise, characterized by the number of the working population, its professional and educational level, and other qualitative characteristics. [1] The factors of formation, use, development and production of labor potential have social, legal, economic, demographic, organizational and informational components [2]. During the war, the labor potential of Ukraine was reduced by a third [3]. Before the war, the labor force of Ukraine was 17.4 million people (9.1 million men and 8.3 million women of working age), but with the beginning of a full-scale war with the Russian Federation, the situation changed dramatically. As of the beginning of 2023, there were 4.6 million Ukrainians outside the country, of which 3.2 million were women of working age. 3 million people lived in the territories temporarily occupied from the beginning of 2022, of which approximately 1.3 million are of working age. Another 1 million citizens were mobilized into the army and other military formations. That is, since the beginning of the full-scale invasion, Ukraine has lost access to 5.5 million people of working age. This is slightly more than 30% of the entire workforce.

As of the beginning of the year, out of 11.9 million people in the workforce in Ukraine, 7.9-8.8 million were in permanent residence - only 45-50% of the pre-war population of working age. Separation of unresolved aspects of the problem. Obtaining up-to-date information on trends in the labor market in a country where there is a war, the number and composition of the workforce is changing, is a difficult task, given that even taking into account the outflow of several million able-bodied refugees, Ukraine still has a high level of unemployment [4,5,6].

The purpose of the study is to provide an assessment of the peculiarities of the formation of the labor potential of Ukraine in the war and post-war period.

Research materials and methods. An assessment of the country's population and its economic activity was carried out based on the data of the State Committee of Statistics of Ukraine, the Center for Medical Statistics of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine, the examination of social and gender programs of the Razumkov Center, operational data of personnel portals and sociological surveys, scientific publications. Official data from the State Statistics Service are currently not available, preliminary estimates are based on information about territories controlled by Ukraine and exclude temporarily occupied territories. Thus, the

State Statistics Service of Ukraine informs that, taking into account the situation that has developed in connection with military aggression, the relevant statistical information will be made public after the deadline for submitting statistical and financial reports, established by the Law of Ukraine "On the Protection of the Interests of the Subjects of Reporting and Other Documents during the period of martial law or a state of war" [7]. Employment of the population in the labor process, demographic indicators are determined [8].

The results. In wartime, the dependence of increasing risks and the uncertainty of the free movement of production factors was revealed, including workforce, which led to the destruction of labor market institutions and their effective functioning. Problems in the economy, combined with significant internal movements in the country and flows of refugees, lead to an increase in the level of unemployment, social exclusion, discrimination in the workplace, including in relation to young people, the spread of poverty, etc. According to the State Statistics Service of Ukraine, after the beginning of the occupation of certain regions of Ukraine by the Russian Federation, the number of the employed population decreased by 4.1-4.6% in accordance with 2013. The highest level of employment was observed among citizens aged 40-49 (77.2%), and the lowest - among people aged 60-70 (13.1%) and young people aged 15-24 (25.1%). The dynamics of the employed population show that it decreased by 37.2% from 1995, when its number was 23.7 million people, in 2021 - 14.9 million, in 2022 - 10.5 million. This decrease in the number of the employed population is associated with the "curtailment" of some types of production, the closing of enterprises, the "shifting" of potential working hours to the shadow economy, as well as to work abroad, to the cohort of the unemployed, to the unproductive sphere, and the conduct of military operations. The number of informally employed citizens aged 15-70 in 2021 was equal to 3.1 million people, or 19.6% of all employed citizens. Among women, the share of people employed in the informal sector of the economy was 16.5%, among men - 22.4% [8]. The level of unemployment in the age group of 15-70 years (according to the ILO methodology) has been increasing in recent years. An important demographic indicator characterizing the labor potential is the population mortality rate. According to the State Statistics Committee of Ukraine, the mortality rate of the population of Ukraine is one of the highest in the world and Europe (14.5-15.9% in some years). The mortality of persons of working age significantly reduces the average life expectancy of men (OL), most of them (70%) die between the ages of 30 and 60. A third of the population does not live to the end of the period of labor activity (65 years). Mortality among the civilian population and military personnel in wartime will be reflected in the average life expectancy in the following years. In the age structure of the population, people under the age of 14 make up 13.7% of the total population, compared to 22.7% in previous years, which indicates a decrease in the reserve of labor potential in the future, which threatens the collapse of production personnel, especially in such industries, as a metallurgical, chemical and coke-

chemical, coal, mining and beneficiation, energy industry. The coefficient of potential replacement (child burden coefficient) is calculated as the ratio of the number of the population below the working age to the number of the working population - for Ukraine it is only 19.4%[9]. The total number of the population will decrease, almost half of it will be people over 45 years old.

The loss and damage of production assets and infrastructure, the interruption of supply chains of trade networks weakened the potential of the labor market, which led to the loss of employment opportunities for the majority of Ukrainians. Small businesses have fewer opportunities to financially support their workforce, small and medium-sized businesses in Ukraine have already cut 1.07 million employees. Relocation and forced migration have led to a change in the structure of the labor market, as well as the structure of offers and the saturation of specialists across regions. The number of jobs decreased in the regions most affected by the military aggression of the Russian Federation. The imbalance between labor supply and demand has become significant. Due to the war, there is a decrease in wages. The share of the population with incomes lower than the actual living wage, which for working-age persons in 2022 is UAH 2,481, it can reach 70%.

The development of the labor potential in the post-war period involves: improving material security due to the investigation of the investment climate, support and development of small and medium-sized businesses, increasing the value of the national workforce; financing of scientific, technical and innovative activities, the formation of scientific personnel potential, the creation of legal conditions and the development of innovative infrastructure; improvement of the demographic situation, promotion of health: improvement of occupational health and safety, creation of safe, favorable working conditions and bringing the norms of labor legislation in accordance with EU legislation, increasing the level of medical care for workers; regulation of the labor market: ensuring effective employment with the concentration of labor resources in competitive industries, social protection of the employed and unemployed, taking into account the European experience. Prognostic expectations for the development of the labor potential depend on when the war will end and under what scenario the country will develop.

Conclusions and proposals.1. The working-age population forms the labor potential of Ukraine. The workforce before the war was about 17 million people. But since the beginning of the full-scale invasion, Ukraine has lost access to 5.5 million people of working age. This is more than 30% of the entire labor force. In the age structure of the population, persons under 14 years of age accounted for 13.7% by 2021, which indicates a decrease in the reserve of labor potential in the future. The war exacerbated the processes of the demographic crisis due to a decrease in the birth rate, an increase in the death rate, a reduction in the average life expectancy, and a negative increase in the population, which will adversely affect the reproduction of the labor potential of several subsequent generations, as was

the case after the famine, the Second World War, and the accident at the Central Power Plant.

2. During the war, the demand for labor decreased sharply due to the impossibility of working in war zones, forced migration, relocation or closure of enterprises. reductions in demand for goods and services, problems with logistics and the uncertainty of the future.

3. Increasing the level of employment should become a central issue of post-war reconstruction, reintegration and processes of returning to peace. The process of recovery and restructuring will require a redistribution of the labor force between sectors of the economy, which will allow to increase its level of productivity. It is necessary to develop a special State program for the restoration of the economy, in particular, the restoration of infrastructure, the attraction of foreign investments to provide housing for the affected citizens, especially in the regions of Eastern Ukraine.

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